

Supporting Information

Operando Scanning SAXS/WAXS Cell Design for Multi-Scale Analysis of All-Solid-State Battery Systems

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Sister Cell Scanning S/WAXS Analysis

Figure S1. Scanning SAXS/WAXS analysis of the sister cell. (a) Evolution of WAXS intensity over time during cell operation, showing phase changes in the anode, separator, and cathode. The leftmost panel displays the potential profile, while the rightmost panel presents the relative integrated intensity of Li_2S formation. (b) Spatial distribution of Li_2S at different states of discharge (SODC). The intensity scale represents the relative integrated Li_2S signal, highlighting variations in deposition. (c) Potential profile showing discharge (blue) and charge (red) cycles with vertical dotted lines marking key transition points. (d) SAXS intensity profiles during discharge as a function of scattering vector q . The intensity within the scattering region associated with the nanopores (highlighted in gray) is stable throughout cycling despite significant chemical transformations. (e) SAXS intensity profiles during charge, demonstrating similar stability to the discharge process. (f) Evolution of Li_2S crystallite size determined from WAXS peak analysis, showing nucleation and growth during discharge followed by dissolution during charge.

Figure S2. Relative WAXS changes in the main cell during galvanostatic cycling. Significant crystal reordering can be observed during the switch from discharge to charge.

Figure S3. Cryo-FIB-SEM workflow. (a) SEM image showing the surface of the free-standing cathode. (b) Deposition of a protective platinum layer on the region of interest before milling. (c) FIB milling outlines the lamella structure prior to extraction. (d) The extracted lamella after thinning, showing a cross-section with a window milled to approximately 100 nm thickness. Annotations highlight different phases, including large solid electrolyte particles within the carbon-sulfur composite, suggesting incomplete homogenization during ball milling.

Cryo-Focused Ion Beam Scanning Electron Microscopy (Cryo-FIB-SEM) was performed at ScopeM using a Helios NanoLab 600i dual-beam microscope (FEI/Thermo Fisher Scientific). Lamellae were prepared from a free-standing cathode (see main Methods section for electrode fabrication details) to investigate the distribution of solid electrolyte and carbon within the cathode structure.

The electrode material was fixed onto carbon tape within an argon-filled glovebox ($O_2 < 0.1$ ppm, $H_2O < 0.1$ ppm) to minimize exposure to air and moisture. Samples were subsequently transferred to the FIB-SEM instrument under Argon atmosphere and while still at room temperature using an EM VCT100 vacuum cryo transfer system (Leica). During all cryo-FIB-SEM operations, the stage was cooled to and maintained at approximately -150°C under high vacuum conditions (pressure $< 3 \times 10^{-6}$ mbar).

For lamella preparation, a region of interest on the cathode surface was selected (Figure S3a). Prior to milling and still at room temperature, this selected area was coated with a protective platinum (Pt) layer approximately 3 μm thick, deposited using ion beam-induced deposition (Figure S3b). This Pt layer served to protect the underlying active material during the subsequent ion milling process.

SEM imaging was performed throughout lamella fabrication at an acceleration voltage of 3 kV using secondary electron (SE) detectors (ETD or ICE) with the sample at a working distance of 4 mm. After cooling the system initial coarse milling steps to define the lamella (Figure S3c shows an intermediate stage) were carried out using a 30 kV Ga^+ ion beam, with beam currents of 9 nA and 2.5 nA for milling of the trenches and to cut the lamella free from the electrode material.

This process yielded a lamella of about 15 μm by 15 μm (width height) by 3 μm thickness, ensuring mechanical stability for lift-out and attachment to a TEM grid. To mount the lamella onto the manipulator for lift out and finally to the TEM grid a GIS (gas injector system, to introduce the Pt precursor gas into the specimen chamber for ion beam induced deposition) free welding technique has been applied as standard ion beam induced deposition techniques do not work under cryo conditions (Figure C.3d shows the lamella after lift-out and mounting). A thin electron-transparent window, approximately 5 μm in lateral size, was then prepared within the lamella by gentle fine-milling using progressively reduced ion beam voltages and currents (starting with 30 kV, 230 pA, 8 kV, 21 pA, and finally 5 kV, 15 pA), a method suitable for minimizing damage in sensitive structures. The final window thickness was targeted to be ~ 100 – 200 nm, as verified by electron transparency observed during 2 kV SEM imaging. At this stage, clear material contrast between the carbon-sulfur mixture and solid electrolyte particles became apparent in the thinned window (as visible in the thinned region of Figure S3d).

While transmission electron microscopy (TEM) measurements were initially attempted on these cryo-lamellae, this approach was not pursued further in this project due to challenges associated with maintaining window integrity and the observed beam sensitivity of the electrolyte material under TEM conditions.

Figure S4. Reference SAXS and WAXS patterns for battery components. SAXS (left panel): The LiPSCI electrolyte (brown) shows weak scattering that flattens to the background level at high- q , suggesting limited nanostructure. The carbon host (black) displays a strong scattering signature characteristic of high porosity. The pristine cathode composite (grey) exhibits significantly lower scattering intensity than the pure carbon, attributed to pore filling by sulfur. WAXS (right panel): The LiPSCI electrolyte (brown) presents sharp diffraction peaks, indicating good crystallinity. The carbon host (black) is predominantly amorphous. In the cathode composite (grey), peaks from the LiPSCI phase are evident but are substantially broader than in the pure electrolyte, indicative of smaller crystallite sizes within the cathode.

Cell Design

Figure S5. Cell Design Iterations. (a) Initial cell design with (b) a smaller spring cup. The springs in that size could not deliver the required pressure. (c) The final spring cup design allowed for larger, stronger springs.

Figure S6. Pellet press. External press made from stainless steel to form the Li-In anode layer and combine it with the solid electrolyte to form a Li-In / electrolyte pellet.

Technical Challenges in Liquid Electrolyte Measurements

While our *operando* SAXS/WAXS cell was designed specifically for solid-state batteries, we conducted measurements on a liquid-electrolyte Li-S system as a control experiment to validate the cell's capability to detect SAXS changes when present. This adaptation was not intended for detailed mechanistic investigation of liquid Li-S batteries but rather to confirm that the absence of SAXS changes in the solid-state system was not an experimental artifact. Nevertheless, this adaptation presented several technical challenges that limited our ability to collect complete cycling data.

Pressure Control and Electrolyte Volume Management

The fundamental issue encountered in adapting our cell for liquid electrolyte systems was the inverse relationship between electrolyte volume and pressure control. Unlike solid-state systems where pressure is applied mechanically, liquid systems introduce hydrostatic pressure considerations that are difficult to manage in a confined *operando* cell environment.

We encountered two competing constraints:

Limited electrolyte volume: Using minimal quantities of liquid electrolyte requires thin separators (PE/PP). However, thin separators led to rapid lithium dendrite formation. Additionally, limited electrolyte volume caused early polysulfide saturation, prematurely terminating the discharge process at the first voltage plateau (~2.3V).

Higher electrolyte volume: Sufficient electrolyte quantity is necessary for proper sulfur dissolution during the liquid Li-S battery operation. This higher electrolyte volume requires a suitable separator such as glass fiber (Whatman) that can accommodate the liquid while providing better protection against dendrite formation. However, the increased electrolyte volume created hydrostatic pressure within the confined cell, which disrupted electrical contacts and interfacial stability, compromising electrochemical performance.

Uneven pressure distribution from the thickness differences across the battery stack could further enhance the dendrite formation.

Separator Selection Trade-offs

The separator material selection introduced additional complications:

Glass fiber separators: These offer better accommodation of the required electrolyte volume and improved dendrite suppression due to their thickness. However, their use in our confined cell geometry led to hydrostatic pressure issues described above.

Polymer separators (PE/PP): Though allowing operation with reduced electrolyte volumes, they provided minimal protection against dendrite formation.

Implications for Data Collection

Figure S7. Operando SAXS/WAXS imaging of a liquid electrolyte Li-S battery. a) Time-resolved SAXS (center) and WAXS (right) data during galvanostatic discharge with the corresponding voltage profile (left). The charging cycle was interrupted due to the formation of Li dendrites. The WAXS data shows the formation and dissolution of Li_2S (peak at $q \approx 20 \text{ nm}^{-1}$), while the SAXS data exhibits pronounced intensity changes in the low- q region, indicating sulfur dissolution into the liquid electrolyte during discharge.

These technical challenges limited our ability to collect complete cycling data for the liquid system. However, the partial discharge data obtained was sufficient for its intended purpose: confirming that our cell design can detect SAXS signal changes when they occur. This validation strengthens our interpretation that the absence of SAXS changes in the solid-state system genuinely reflects its reaction mechanism rather than any limitation of our experimental setup.

It's worth noting that these challenges are not unique to our cell design but represent common difficulties in developing *operando* cells for liquid electrolyte systems, particularly those requiring tight control over electrolyte volume and distribution. Our experience highlights the inherent advantages of solid-state configurations for *operando* X-ray studies, where pressure can be applied mechanically and maintained without concerns about electrolyte redistribution or hydrostatic effects.

SAXS Contrast Calculation

To quantitatively support the interpretation of the stable SAXS profiles observed during electrochemical cycling, we performed an estimation of the expected change in scattering contrast based on the measured discharge capacity.

Theoretical Background

The intensity of Small-Angle X-ray Scattering (SAXS) is proportional to the square of the difference in the scattering length density (SLD, or ρ) between the carbon matrix and the contents of its nanopores.

$$\text{SAXS Intensity} \propto (\Delta\rho)^2 = (\rho_{\text{carbon}} - \rho_{\text{pore content}})^2$$

A small change in the effective SLD of the pore content ($\rho_{\text{pore content}}$) will result in a minor, likely undetectable, change in the SAXS signal.

Calculation and Values

The calculation is based on the following established material properties and experimental assumptions:

- Initial State (Charged): Based on prior work, we assume the carbon nanopores are initially 50% filled by volume with sulfur (S).
- Conversion (Discharged): Based on the measured discharge capacity, we assume that approximately 1/3 of the initial sulfur is electrochemically converted to lithium sulfide (Li_2S).

Table S1. Scattering Length Density Values

Property	Carbon (C)	Sulfur (S)	Li_2S
SLD (ρ) [10^{11} cm^{-2}]	1.74	1.69	1.34
Molar Volume [cm^3/mol]	-	15.5	27.7

SLD of the Charged Pore

In the charged state, the pore is 50% filled with sulfur. The effective SLD of the pore content is:

$$\rho_{\text{pore initial}} = 0.50 * \rho_S = 0.50 * 1.69 \times 10^{11} = 0.845 \times 10^{11} \text{ cm}^{-2}$$

Volume Change upon Conversion

The conversion of sulfur to Li_2S involves significant volume expansion. The volume ratio is:

$$\text{Volume Ratio} = \frac{V_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}}}{V_S} = \frac{27.7}{15.5} = 1.79$$

This means that 1 unit of sulfur volume becomes 1.79 units of Li_2S volume.

SLD of the Discharged Pore

We assume that in the discharged state, 1/3 of the initial sulfur volume has been converted to Li_2S , and 2/3 remains as sulfur. This corresponds to a capacity of 1/3 of sulfur's theoretical capacity.

- Volume of remaining S: $(2/3) * 0.50$ (initial S vol.) = 0.333 (33.3% of pore volume)
- Volume of new Li_2S : $(1/3) * 0.50$ (initial S vol.) * 1.79 (expansion) = 0.298 (29.8% of pore volume)

The effective SLD of the discharged pore is the weighted average of these two components:

$$\begin{aligned}\rho_{\text{pore discharged}} &= (V_S * \rho_S) + (V_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}} * \rho_{\text{Li}_2\text{S}}) = (0.333 * 1.69 \times 10^{11}) + (0.298 * 1.34 \times 10^{11}) \\ &= (0.563 \times 10^{11}) + (0.399 \times 10^{11}) = 0.962 \times 10^{11} \text{ cm}^{-2}\end{aligned}$$

Comparison and Conclusion

The calculation shows that the effective SLD of the pore content changes very little between the charged and discharged states.

Table S2. Calculated SAXS contrast for different pore filling scenarios. The contrast term $(\Delta\rho)^2$ is calculated relative to the carbon matrix.

State	Effective Pore SLD (10^{11} cm^{-2})	SAXS Contrast $(\Delta\rho)^2$ (10^{22} cm^{-4})	Change in Signal
Charged (50% S)	0.845	$(1.74 - 0.845)^2 = 0.801$	---
Discharged (S + Li_2S)	0.962	$(1.74 - 0.962)^2 = 0.605$	-24.50%

The effective SLD of the pore changes by only 0.117×10^{11} upon partial discharge. This results in a calculated SAXS contrast decrease of approximately 25%. While not zero, this moderate change in scattering intensity is likely to be undetectable within the overall scattering pattern, which is dominated by other cell components and the initial contrast drop from pore filling. Note that an intensity decrease of about a factor of 1.25 is comparably little on the logarithmic SAXS intensity scaling. Therefore, this quantitative estimation supports our interpretation that the stable SAXS profile is consistent with a confined, intrapore reaction where the change in scattering contrast is too minor to be resolved.